

Marketing and Convergence

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Marketing is, and will continue to be, heavily influenced by IT, and marketers who do not adapt to this new technological era will not survive¹. The common perception was that with the internet, everything will change², that new rules would apply³ and that we would step over into a 'New' or 'Digital Economy'⁴. The rules of technology, business, and marketing were different. It said that forget ROI, build market share. Forget mass marketing; develop a personal relationship. Forget the traditional consumer; focus on the "cyber-consumer." And those who don't believe this were said to be stuck in past.

It is clear now that the Internet doesn't transform everything. But we cannot forget that it *does* create major changes in the way consumers behave and how the business operates⁵. The power of the latest technology creates basically new possibilities for consumers and companies. If we begin to look beyond the either/or view of the world, we see a rich and complex set of opportunities. The challenge is sorting through the interactions between consumers and technology to find these opportunities. The greatest opportunities are through a fusion of the old and the new, physical and virtual.

It is still too early to judge the quality of much that has been written about the impact of the Internet on business. However, the literature on this subject has been replete with

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¹Boshoff, C. and Terbanche, N. (1996), "Measuring consumer sentiment towards marketing: the New Zealand Marketing Index", Proceedings of the 25th EMAC Conference ± Marketing for an Expanding Europe, European Marketing Academy, Budapest University of Economic Science, Budapest, pp. 99-107.

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² Markus, M. L. (2000): Paradigm Shifts – E-Business and Business/Systems Integration, Communications of the AIS, Vol. 4, No. 10, <http://cais.isworldnet.org>.

³ Kelly, K. (1997): New Rules for the New Economy, Wired, Vol. 5, No. 9, <http://www.wired.com/wired/5.09/newrules.html>.

⁴ Tapscott, D. (1995): "The Digital Economy: Promise and Peril in the Age of Networked Intelligence", McGraw-Hill, New York.

⁵ Kanter (2001, pp. 3-4) Kanter, R.M. (2001), *Evolve! Succeeding in the Digital Culture of Tomorrow*, Harvard Business School Press, Boston, MA.

fairly dramatic predictions. Achrol and Kotler⁶ (1999) described the continued growth of electronic commerce as the single biggest opportunity and threat facing almost every industry. Early writers on the subject, such as Hamel and Sampler⁷ (1998), predicted that the Internet would change the relationship between producers and consumers and saw business as entering the new Internet age in which companies can no longer rely solely on the traditional bricks and mortar model⁸ (Lord, 2000). Porter⁹ (2001) suggested that companies have no choice but to deploy Internet technology if they want to remain competitive.

Many organizations initially treated e-business as just another offering. Pure-play Internet firms saw it as separate. But in fact, the most powerful new models may not be those based on such a concept, but rather on a deeper combination. This is like mixture of where green and blue, or yellow and red are joined together to create a new color, which is more useful and attractive. Similarly, E-business and traditional business can be brought together to create something new and different, and individual consumers are combining the two in ways that fit their individual interest.

These days all such combinations work and the success lie in experimenting with the different combinations. E-business and dot-com revolution is one example of such experimentation where companies tested what worked out and what didn't. Investors also responded by pouring capital into these markets where some succeeded and some failed.

The changing nature of marketing

Marketing, by nature, should be a creative and adaptive discipline that is constantly regenerating itself (Brownlie et al.¹⁰, 1994; Rapp and Collins¹¹, 1995; Cronin¹², 1995). Some contend that the very tenets of marketing will, and should be, changed and developed (Brownlie and Saren¹³, 1995; Brownlie et al.¹⁴, 1994; Brown et al.¹⁵, 1996).

⁶ Achrol, R.S. and Kotler, P. (1999), "Marketing in the network economy", *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 63, Special Issue, pp. 146-63.

⁷ Hamel, G. and Sampler, J. (1998), "The e-corporation (online e-commerce building a new industrial order)", *Fortune*, December 7, p. 80.

⁸ Lord, C. (2000), "The practicalities of developing a successful e-business strategy", *Journal of Business Strategy*, Vol. 21 No. 2, p. 40.

⁹ Porter, M.E. (2001), "Strategy and the Internet", *Harvard Business Review*, March, pp. 63-78.

¹⁰ Brownlie, D., Saren, M., Whittington, R. and Wensley, R. (1994), "The new marketing myopia: critical perspectives on theory and research in marketing ± introduction", *European Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 28 No. 3, pp. 6-12.

¹¹ Rapp, S. and Collins, S. (1995), *The New Maxi-Marketing*, McGraw-Hill, New York, NY.

¹² Cronin, M.J. (1995), *Doing More Business on the Internet ± How the Electronic Highway is Transforming American Companies*, Van Nostrand Reinhold, New York, NY.

¹³ Brownlie, D. and Saren, M. (1995), "On the commodification of marketing knowledge: opening themes", *Journal of Marketing Management*, Vol. 11 No. 7, pp. 619-27.

¹⁴ Brownlie, D., Saren, M., Whittington, R. and Wensley, R. (1994), "The new marketing myopia: critical perspectives on theory and research in marketing ± introduction", *European Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 28 No. 3, pp. 6-12.

Alternatively, there is the argument that traditional marketing practices will continue ± right product, place, promotion and price. What are changing are the techniques by which the marketing mix variables are realised (Murray and O'Driscoll¹⁶, 1996; Hamilton¹⁷, 1995). One view of this era's impact on marketing is that the search for a new marketing paradigm has begun (Mitchell¹⁸, 1994; O'Malley and Patterson¹⁹, 1998; Piercy²⁰, 1998). This is similarly observed in the relationship marketing literature where many contend that a new and genuine transformation is taking place (Tzokas and Saren²¹, 1997; Sheth and Parvatiyar²², 1995; Webster²³, 1992). It is interesting that marketing has traditionally been slow to change and to capitalise on IT (Mitchell²⁴, 1994; Peattie and Peters²⁵, 1998). It now appears that it is embracing IT "with a zeal and exponential enthusiasm unparalleled" in its history (Deans²⁶, 1997).

Convergence of Customerization and Standardization

Products are now so bound up with associated services that it is possible to customize the "bundle" to individual requirements. This process is termed mass customization, and it is viable because Internet technology allows the economies of scale and capacity of mass production to be retained²⁷. Mass customization is therefore the antithesis of mass marketing which dominated the twentieth century, and it allows the customer to become intimately involved in the design and production process within an organization.

¹⁵ Brownlie, B. and Saren, M. (1997), "Beyond the one dimensional marketing manager", *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, Vol. 28 No. 3, pp. 6-12.

¹⁶ Murray, J. and O'Driscoll, A. (1996), *Strategy and Process in Marketing*, Gill and Macmillan, Dublin.

¹⁷ Hamilton (1995), quoted in Sterne, J. (1995), *World Wide Web Marketing ± Integrating the Internet into your Marketing Strategy*, John Wiley and Sons, New York, NY.

¹⁸ Mitchell, A. (1994), "Marketing's new model army", *Management Today*, March, pp. 42-9.

¹⁹ O'Malley, L. and Patterson, M. (1998), "Vanishing point: the mix management paradigm reviewed", *Journal of Marketing Management*, Vol. 14 No. 8, pp. 829-51.

²⁰ Piercy, N. (1998), "Marketing implementation: the implications of marketing paradigm weakness for the strategy execution process", *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, Vol. 26 No. 3, pp. 222-36.

²¹ Tzokas, N. and Saren, M. (1997), "Building relationship platforms in consumer markets: a value chain approach", *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, Vol. 5 No. 2, pp. 105-20.

²² Sheth, J.N. and Parvatiyar, A. (1995), "The evolution of relationship marketing", *International Business Review*, Vol. 4 No. 4, pp. 397-418.

²³ Webster, F.W. (1992), "The changing role of marketing in the corporation", *Journal of Marketing*, No. 56, pp. 1-17.

²⁴ Mitchell, A. (1994), "Marketing's new model army", *Management Today*, March, pp. 42-9.

²⁵ Peattie, K. and Peters, L. (1997), "The marketing mix in the third age of computing", *Marketing Intelligence and Planning*, Vol. 15 No. 3, pp. 142-50.

²⁶ Deans, K.R. (1997), "The Internet ± the new strategic marketing tool? Some survey results", *Proceedings of the Academy of Marketing 31st Annual Conference, Marketing Without Borders*, Vol. 2, July, pp. 1279-81

²⁷ Chaffey, D. *et al.* (2000), *Internet Marketing*, Financial Times/Prentice-Hall, London.

Customers have become co-producers in evolving customized products and services with the help of powerful new technologies. New technologies also allow customers to customize messages that they receive and permit companies to personalize the messages that they deliver. While such tailoring was once offered led to very high cost, the technology makes such customization much cheaper and easier. Taking from jeans to coffee, to bicycles, to eyewear, to cosmetics, to vitamins, to breakfast cereals, companies have used this technology to create customized offerings. The pioneers of this technology saw it as a nearly certain win. Due to this customers could get exactly what they want, hence they won't have to settle for some less-than-perfect standardized offering or message and at the same time if companies could manufacture to order, the inventory reduction would go directly to the bottom line.

However, standardized products have also not gone away. And we could find that there are reasons why people like off-the-shelf offerings, at least in certain areas of their lives. There are cases where product or service may not be important enough to necessitate the time and energy of customization, and customers may have an unstated need, so they may not know what they want until they observe it or they might like themselves to fit into a crowd, with popular music or a global brand. They might like to engage in an experience that they don't need to design themselves. For example, many customers would prefer to a readymade menu rather than suggesting customized food.

Companies can use a variety of strategies to combine standardization and "customerization" (the customization of both offerings and messages). Companies can keep their standardized offerings a click away from their customized programs. They can offer exterior customization, such as different faceplates and ring tones for cellular phones, without basically transforming the underlying offering. They can invite the customer into the lab to actively engage in creating the new product.

Convergence in Promotion

The established tools of promotion, such as advertising, sales promotion and direct marketing have been augmented by the development of the technology, which has offered the potential to communicate with many customers. Telephone marketing, e-mail and mobile telephony, as well as digital TV and the Internet, have supplemented these traditional tools. In order to maximise the effectiveness of the tools, cohesive integration is needed (Cornelisessen and Lock²⁸, 2001). The synergy generated by such integration far outweighs the use of individual tools in isolation, although it has been suggested that the Internet has increased effectiveness and efficiency in communicating with customers (Hardaker and Graham²⁹, 2001). Websites have the potential to give information, to entertain and be interactive in their communication. Hence, the use of integrated communications and the subsequent development of such use means that a user can experience a range of different media when viewing an organisation's website – graphics,

²⁸ Cornelisessen, J. and Lock, A. (2001), "The appeal of integration: managing communications in modern organizations", *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, Vol. 19 No. 6, pp. 425-31.

²⁹ Hardaker, G. and Graham, G. (2001), *Wired Marketing: Energising Business for e-Commerce*, Wiley, New York, NY.

video clips, music, text, speech and, sometimes, virtual reality (Adams and Clark³⁰, 2001).

The organisation/customer relationship is enabled by the creation of trust in an electronic environment (Chadwick³¹, 2001). Allan and Chudry³² (2000) state that the Internet is an excellent channel for communicating with customers on an individual basis because of its immediate and direct interaction capability. Integration of all marketing communication tools is as important in electronic marketing as it is in the non-virtual world. The ultimate role of direct marketing is to gain a response. The Internet has the advantage of being able to solicit such responses in real time and enables providers to interact with potential and actual consumers as well as enabling intra-customer communications. This interaction has sparked further debate on the possibility of one-to-one marketing (Caccavale³³, 2000) with a view to developing strong and lasting relationships with loyal customers. Such tailored messages are reliant upon the mining of large amounts of data (Agrawal et al.³⁴, 2001) and, hence, may be the domain of larger, more readily resourced organisations.

Even media is capitalizing on technology and co-creation with television consumers. TV networks, for one have taken advantage of text messaging in shaping the plot of their shows much like the creative approach of *Sana'y Wala Nang Wakas* that paved the way for an interactive soap opera with its loyal viewers. Another is the highly popular Emmy nominated reality show *American Idol* that kept Filipino viewers in the US and Hawaii glued to their seats weekly and whose text messaging rallied Jasmine Trias to finish in the final three.

Convergence of Virtual and Physical Communities

The Internet creates the opportunity to develop virtual communities that draw together people with common interests across continents. The power of these communities has been demonstrated, but the members of these communities are also members of physical communities. The first convergence challenge is the opportunity for these physical and virtual communities to be fused in different ways. A second convergence challenge is to fuse the social mission of many of these communities with an economic purpose.

For example, Sulekha.com grew organically to become one of the largest Indian online communities, reaching 20 million people of Indian heritage in 70 countries around the

³⁰ Adams, T. and Clark, N. (2001), *The Internet: Effective Online Communication*, Harcourt College Publishers, Orlando, FL.

³¹ Chadwick, S.A. (2001), "Communicating trust in e-commerce interactions", *Management Communication Quarterly*, Vol. 14 No. 4, pp. 653-8.

³² Allan, S. and Chudry, F. (2000), "The Internet: a fad or a fundamental for relationship marketing?", *Journal of Database Marketing*, Vol. 8 No. 1, pp. 73-86.

³³ Caccavale, M. (2000), "Exploiting interactive marketing", *Interactive Marketing*, Vol. 1 No. 3, pp. 277-83.

³⁴ Agrawal, V., Arjona, L.D. and Lemmens, R. (2001), "E-commerce: the path to rational exuberance", *McKinsey Quarterly*, Vol. 1, pp. 31-43.

world. But it faced two challenges: integrating its online community into the fabric of existing Indian communities and developing a viable economic business while preserving the social strength of the community. To better merge the online and offline communities, Sulekha partnered with local Indian communities and offered tickets to events such as Indian music and theater. The company also is working on a system to combine travel services with community. For example, an Indian immigrant in England who wants her elderly parents to visit might use Sulekha to arrange for a community member traveling in the same direction to serve as a companion on the journey. By combining the community with commerce, the site creates a unique offering that adds value for community members while ensuring that they book their travel through the site. Buy tickets and send companion with parents.

The convergence of virtual and physical, social and economic is where many of the rich opportunities of communities lie. Companies need to take advantage of the strengths and weaknesses of physical and virtual communities to design coherent offerings that invite interaction between the two in ways that support corporate and business objectives.

Convergence of Online and Offline Channels

Customers want to "call, click, or visit," with seamless interaction across online and offline channels. They expect to be recognized and engage in a continuous dialogue with the company across all these channels, in person, on the phone, on the Internet, or through wireless channels. Companies need to design strategies that combine the strengths of online and offline approaches.

Companies can let customers decide how they want to interact. For example, Barnes & Noble and other bookstores have kiosks in stores that give customers access to the company's entire online database and warehouse. If a book is in the store, the system shows where it is located. Or, customers can jump off the terminal and browse the aisles of the store or sit in the cafe. The customer has many options for interacting with the company, online and offline in the same physical location or anywhere at anytime using bn.com.

The best channel for interacting with the customer often depends on the context for the interaction. For example, 75 percent of electronic selling for Domino's pizza in the United Kingdom is done through interactive television. Why? Because people are most actively watching television at the time they are thinking about ordering pizza.

Companies also have to create seamless interactions and be sure to treat customers the same across different channels. For example, a customer who fills out a loan application online should be offered an update on the status the next time she calls or visits the ATM. To develop these channels, companies have to develop the right brand or set of brands and use partnerships or alliances to complement their weaknesses. They need to create a "fusion" of different channels to provide a coherent experience or set of experiences to customers.

Convergence in Distribution

A notable implication for marketers is the potential to shift from a non-virtual marketplace to a market-space instead, incorporating virtual transaction/distribution spaces (Lockett and Blackman³⁵, 2001). The ability of a website to establish contact with and subsequently serve customers has been hailed by many as a cost-reducing way of distributing goods/services direct from the provider to the consumer. Hence, the potential of the Internet has been seen to be exciting and, for some, the opportunity to enter new markets which had previously been inaccessible to them (Allan and Chudry³⁶,2000).

Retailers offering both a physical retail outlet and the opportunity to buy from an online facility are becoming more prevalent. In some markets (e.g. grocery), the two forms of distribution work hand-in-hand. Indeed, the synergy created by the use of multi-channels can out-perform the “pure-play” (online only) retailers (Vishwanath and Mulvin³⁷, 2001). Research by Balabanis and Vassileiou³⁸ (1999) determined that consumers from the higher income brackets were likely candidates for purchase through the Internet, but only from retailers with recognized brands. Hence, it is likely that the most successful online retailers will be those organizations that also have a physical presence in the high street/shopping centres.

Convergence of New Competitive Value Equations and Traditional Pricing

Companies such as eBay and Priceline have offered new pricing models such as auctions or name-your-own-price. But people don't buy exclusively through these channels, so consumers combine traditional seller-initiated pricing with these new buyer-initiated pricing models. Customers might purchase through Priceline for some trips but still go through an online agent or a physical travel agent for others.

Companies are finding ways to combine traditional seller-initiated pricing with buyer-initiated pricing models. For example, eBay offers its sellers the opportunity to add a "Buy It Now" button that allows customers to shut down the auction before it starts and buy the product at a fixed price. In this way, the site combines seller-initiated fixed prices with more dynamic buyer-initiated pricing.

Companies are also redefining the value equation by adding information, entertainment, and education to their traditional value propositions. The value equation has become more complex. The new value equation is based on a variety of sources of value,

³⁵ Lockett, A. and Blackman, I. (2001), “Strategies for building a customer base on the Internet: symbiotic marketing”, *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, Vol. 9, pp. 47-68.

³⁶ Allan, S. and Chudry, F. (2000), “The Internet: a fad or a fundamental for relationship marketing?”, *Journal of Database Marketing*, Vol. 8 No. 1, pp. 73-86.

³⁷ Vishwanath, J. and Mulvin, G. (2001), “Multi-channels: the real winners in the B2C Internet wars”, *Business Strategy Review*, Vol. 12 No. 1, pp. 25-33.

³⁸ Balabanis, G. and Vassileiou, S. (1999), “Some attitudinal predictors of home-shopping through the Internet”, *Journal of Marketing Management*, Vol. 15, pp. 361-85.

including the product/service offering itself, service, the brand, speed, 24 x 7 availability and other aspects of convenience, ease of use, novelty, peace of mind, experience and entertainment, information in context, education and professional growth, and control—all balanced against price. There is also value created from the convergence of online and offline businesses working together.

In addition, companies are combining the offering and experience in new ways to create new value propositions. The ambiance of retailers, such as the piano player in Nordstrom, has always been a part of the value equation of the real-world shopping experience. Now online sites are paying more attention to the experience. For example, Swatch offers online buyers the opportunity to design their own "virtual clerk" with diverse faces, eyes, hair styles, and attitudes. BMW commissioned a number of short films by professional directors for its Web site, which only marginally featured its cars. Volkswagen has set up an online radio station. Experience is becoming a critical part of the online value equation.

Convergence of Choice Tools and Human Experts

Powerful new online decision tools give users access to advice that they once could receive only from highly trained human experts. Individuals can assess their investment strategies and monitor their portfolios in real time, and they often have as much or more information than their brokers or other advisors. Consumers have access to search engines, decision tools, and life-management tools. The emergence of these new tools creates a number of convergence challenges.

The first challenge is the *balance* between decision-making tools and experts. The proliferation of search and decision-support tools has raised consumer expectations. How do companies need to change the training and use of human experts as a result? How can companies augment the online search engines and decision-making tools used by consumers with additional tools and personal, expert advice? Companies need to increase the sophistication of their human experts or may need to charge for the personal advice that was once part of their total offering. Studies have also found that the use of avatars or other agents online can increase the credibility of their advice.

The second convergence challenge presented by the new decision tools is managing the mix of company messages and third-party information. Customers are exposed to—and still respond to—advertising, PR, and direct marketing messages that are fired at them daily. But these messages are filtered out more rigorously by consumers who have access to independent information and are increasingly skeptical about messages that are piped into their homes and heads. How can companies combine the advertising and spin of traditional marketing communications with third-party information sources? How can they balance the messages that they want customers to hear with the information and insight that consumers want? By offering outside information—including third-party content and competitor information—on their own sites, companies can increase their credibility with customers.

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